

Content-Type: text/html

Reference sequence (query): pediocin_
Identities normalised by aligned length.
Colored by: property

HSP processing: ranked
Search cycle: 2

	bits	E-value	N	100.0%	1:44	
pediocin_						1 [. . . .] 44
1 UniRef50_P29430 Bacteriocin pediocin PA-1 n...	80	3e-14	1	100.0%	1:44	19:62
2 UniRef50_Q9L658 Class IIa bacteriocin EntA ...	40	0.021	1	76.0%	1:25	24:48
3 UniRef50_Q8GR39 Enterocin SE-K4 n=8 Tax=Ent...	40	0.026	1	51.4%	2:36	31:65
4 UniRef50_C2EDS8 Prebacteriocin SkgA2 n=1 Ta...	40	0.028	1	70.4%	1:27	20:46
5 UniRef50_P80925 Bacteriocin mundticin n=9 T...	39	0.037	1	65.0%	1:40	1:40
consensus/100%						
consensus/90%						
consensus/80%						
consensus/70%						

```

1 [ . . . . ] 44
KYYGNVTCGKHSCSVDWGKATTCIINNGAMAWATGGHQGNHKC
KYYGNVTCGKHSCSVDWGKATTCIINNGAMAWATGGHQGNHKC
KYYGNVYCTKNKCTVDWAKATTCI-----
-YYGNVYCNKQKCIWVDWSPARSEIIDRGVKAIVNG-----
RYYGNVTCGKHKCTVNNWQAWTCGVN-----
KYYGNVSCNKKGCSVDWGKAIGIIGNNSAANLATGGAAG----
.YYGNV.CsKptC.VsWupAhs.h.....
.YYGNV.CsKptC.VsWupAhs.h.....
+YYGNVhCsKppCoVDWu+AhopIhs.....
+YYGNVhCsKppCoVDWu+AhopIhs.....

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